

Automatic Coffee Brewing System Using RFID

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Abstract: The automatic coffee brewing system is mainly built with Arduino, sensors, motors and related components. The users can select a custom coffee type and the system automatically makes the coffee type according to the selected menu. RFID technology is integrated, allowing only the authorized users to manage the coffee machine. The ingredients are precisely distributed through servo motors according to the user's selection. The amount of hot water is precisely adjusted and then delivered to the cup. The up and down movement of the stirrer is activated, mixing to achieve a perfect blend. Users only need to select the type of coffee and then the machine arranges it automatically without any manual effort.

Keywords: Automatic Coffee Brewing System, Radio Frequency Identification, Arduino, Sensors, Servo Motors, Stepper Motors, Coffee Machine, Motors.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, automated systems reduce human effort. Therefore, the systems are becoming increasingly important. Humans often experience mental fatigue, tiredness and sleepiness due to daily tasks. The caffeine in coffee is necessary. A cup of coffee makes the mind, boosts energy, and improves mental focus. So humans can continue to do their jobs. The automatic coffee brewing machine provides an effective solution. The system automates the entire process. The user simply selects the type of coffee they want, and the remaining steps of grinding and blending are performed automatically. Using only a few simple steps, users can enjoy freshly brewed coffee without problem. If this machine is placed in offices, factories, and other organizations, employees are easy to use coffee throughout the day.

PROBLEM

With conventional coffee machines, users must manually navigate to the category they want to drink. The machine does not have an LCD display to choose the type. Other machines are not made safe for people with diabetes. And it does not include user-restricted security. This process can be time-consuming and difficult, during busy hours or when preparing multiple drinks. The automatic coffee machine allows the user to simply select their preferred coffee on the LCD screen. Only people within the organization are allowed to use it, external individuals are not permitted. This creativity certifies both convenience and safety for the user. It reduces the risk of errors and saves valuable time during operation. The machine's security features also provide organizations control usage effectively. Overall, it combines technology and convenience to deliver a modern coffee experience. In addition, coffee types suitable for people with diabetes are provided.

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APPROACH

The automatic system provides ease of use and reduces manual effort, incorporating Arduino, sensors, motors, and relevant hardware components. This system is controlled by Arduino Mega board. A 3.5" LCD (Liquid Crystal Display) touch screen for user input and an RFID module for secure access. Servo motors dispense coffee, sugar, and milk accurately, while a NEMA stepper motor positions the cup. A pump supplies hot water. A 28BYJ-48 stepper motor with ULN2003 driver moves the stirrer. A gear motor blends the ingredients to produce a well-mixed coffee. The users can select their preferred type of coffee through a 3.5" LCD shield touch screen, and the system automatically makes the beverage according to the selected menu. Since RFID technology is integrated, only authorized users are allowed to operate the coffee machine. Based on the user's choice, ingredients are accurately dispensed through servo motors. A NEMA stepper motor precisely adjusts the cup position, after which the pump delivers the required amount of hot water. The 28BYJ-48 stepper motor with a ULN2003 driver module operates upward and downward movement of the stirrer, while a gear motor blends the ingredients to achieve a perfect mixture. Therefore, the users only need to select their coffee type, and the machine automatically prepares without manual effort. This system provides a complete and balanced flavor by combining coffee, sugar, and milk according to the user's taste.

Figure 1: Circuit Diagram of Automatic Coffee Brewing System using RFID

Figure 1 is the circuit diagram connection between Arduino Mega and other components such as Thin Film Transistor Liquid Crystal Display, Radio Frequency Identification, Stepper Motor (National Electrical Manufacturer Association), TB6600 Motor driver, Servo Motors, DS1302 Real Time Clock Module, 5V Gear Motor, 12V Mini Water Pump, 2-Channel Relay Module, DC-DC Step Down Module, L298N Motor Driver, Buzzer, 3-Minute Electric Kettle.

Figure 2: Block Diagram of Automatic Coffee Brewing System using RFID

Figure 2 illustrates the block diagram of automatic coffee brewing system using RFID. In this system, TFT LCD, RFID and DC-DC to step-down module are input devices and servo motors, 2-channel relay module, buzzer, TB6600 motor driver module, ULN203 driver module, RTC, L298N motor driver module are output devices.

Figure 3: Flow Chart of Automated Coffee Preparation and Dispensing System

The flow chart of automated coffee preparation and dispensing system is shown in Figure 3.

- If the card is authorized:
 - A stepper motor is rotated.
 - A servo motor is rotated and is back rotated.
- If the card is unauthorized:
 - No further actions are performed.

Figure 4: Flow Chart of Automated Water Heating and Flavor Blending System

The flow chart of automated water heating and flavor blending system is shown in Figure 4.

- If the plug is on, the water will boil and the powder will be stirred.
- If the water runs out, a buzzer will sound.

RESULTS

The implementation design of the system is shown in Figure 8. In the coffee brewing process, when the user scans the RFID card, the selected coffee type is displayed on the TFT-LCD. The RTC module is used to manage the operation time systematically. To accurately move the cup to the correct position, it is controlled by a stepper motor, allowing the cup to automatically shift to the required location. Three servo motors are used to discharge coffee powder, sugar, and milk powder step by step into the cup. For water filling, the 12V motor pump is activated to transfer hot water from the 3-minute electric kettle into the cup. Afterwards, the 5V gear motor is used to stir the mixture of powder and water, ensuring the precise coffee flavor. A 2-channel relay module is applied to control the pump and the kettle, while the NEMA stepper motor is driven by the TB6600 motor driver. When the water inside the kettle runs out, the buzzer generates an alert sound. The entire system is powered by a 12V switching power supply, with DC-to-DC step down modules regulating the required voltage

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levels. Finally, the process is carried out step by step automatically, and a cup of coffee is obtained readily.

Figure 5: Coffee Types are shown on LCD

Figure 5 shows how the user can select the type of coffee they prefer via the touch LCD. There are three types available on the LCD: Sweet Blush, Bold Shot, and Harmony Brew. These represent sweet flavor, bitter flavor, and regular flavor. Users can choose their preferred option. The count means that each time one cup is brewed, the count increases by 1. Even if the power plug is removed and reconnected, the count remains saved in memory and continues from the previous total brewed cups.

Figure 6: Cups controlled by servo motor

Figure 6 illustrates how coffee, sugar and milk powder will be dispensed via servo motors. These three servos will precisely dispense coffee, milk powder, and sugar step by step.

Figure 7: Display stirring rod position

Figure 7 shows a stirring rod that will stir coffee, sugar and milk powder. The stirrer will mix the coffee, milk powder, sugar, and water thoroughly to create a perfect taste.

Figure 8: Design of the system

CONCLUSION

This automatic system is a modern design that reduces the need for manual operation, allowing the users to simply choose their desired type of coffee, after which the process is performed automatically. If this machine is placed in workplaces such as offices, schools, factories, universities, companies, and organizations in Myanmar, it is designed to deliver improved convenience for employees. Since it is intended to use in organizations, RFID technology is available to access the authorize users only. Therefore, only members within the organization are allowed to consume the coffee, while outsiders are not permitted to use this coffee machine. This machine has been systematically developed through step-by-step efforts using the various hardware components.

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